

Crippling teaching and learning culture: The case of teaching English first additional language (EFAL) in rural schools in South Africa

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The Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement's (CAPS) idea of promoting English as the language of learning and teaching (LoLT) in South Africa remains a challenge, particularly in rural schools. Its implementation has caused communication challenges and social exclusion that cripple effective learning, especially in English First Additional classrooms. The enforcement of English as a LoLT in rural schools triggers unsupportive behavioural patterns that cripple pedagogical and epistemological potentials in the classroom. Guided by a sociocultural framework, this study employed observation, focus group discussions, and semi-structured interviews to gather qualitative data. The participants comprised 15 learners and 4 teachers, selected purposively to ensure their suitability from three high schools in Limpopo Province. The study found that a teaching and learning culture devoid of empathy hinders the development of learner autonomy and teacher agency, which are essential for advancing a communicative learning process that the CAPS curriculum aims to achieve.

Keywords: CAPS; Language of Learning and Teaching; Mediation; Teacher Agency; Teacher Empathy

1. Introduction

The crippling culture of teaching and learning that prevails in rural high schools in Limpopo province, South Africa, is a by-product of the mismatches that exist between the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) language policy and classroom practice that ensues when English is used as a language of learning and teaching (LoLT). Nengwai and Molotja (2025) highlight that numerous challenges arise when teachers implement teaching, learning, and assessment policies in English First Additional Language (EFAL) classes. The use of English as a LoLT is a global practice in ELT, pioneered by

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Swain in the 1980s to spread the notion that immersing learners into the habit of learning a language by using it makes them develop their proficiency in it far quicker (Swain, 2019). It is of paramount importance that teachers must balance output and input activities as they complement and reinforce each other during language acquisition (Li et al., 2023). The reason given to justify the efficacy of this learning approach is that it provides learners with more opportunities to hear the target language and practise using it in real-life events, as modelled by significant others who already possess advanced skills in it.

Due to globalisation's compelling demand for functional communication skills required to respond to its needs, numerous countries have endorsed it to prepare their children for future participation in global communication, business, science, and academia, among other areas (Albakri, 2017). This endorsement of English as a bridge to facilitate smooth transnational mobility, communication, and coexistence begins in the classroom, with learners' interaction in the target language (Ernawati et al., 2021). In the past decades, numerous theories on teaching English as a second or additional language were developed as means to improve the performance of learners. Mujumdar (2025) posits that the evolution of language theories/methods/approaches, from grammar translation to the current ones that prioritise the use of digital tools, has transformed language acquisition and developed the language proficiency and competencies of learners.

In the South African educational context, this dream is enforced through the implementation of the CAPS curriculum (CAPS EFAL, 2011), which prescribes the monolingual language policy, its curriculum content, and pedagogical approaches to implement. Despite the efforts made to improve the English language proficiency of learners at primary and secondary school, many of them enrolled at the tertiary level are still struggling to use English effectively. Hence, Meyers (2025) suggested that using micro teaching as a tool at the tertiary level is essential to help pre-service teachers who struggle to adapt in an environment where English is the medium of instruction. To improve the situation, Clark et al. (2021) suggested that institutions of higher learning must provide intensive language programmes aimed at improving the language proficiency of learners. Immersing learners in a language programme has the potential to help them improve their proficiency in English and encourage them to learn better.

Furthermore, studies conducted by Ojo and Mathabathe (2021) in Gauteng province, Spokazi et al. (2021) in the Eastern Cape, and Mabiletsa (2015) in Limpopo to evaluate the effectiveness of CAPS' language policy confirm that using English as a LoLT is fruitful, but largely when applied in private and well-resourced public schools located in urban and semi-urban environments. In

these learning contexts, learners' active participation and negotiation of meaning in interactive oral activities are facilitated by their exposure to an English-medium elementary schooling background. This makes the learning process flow smoothly and naturally because learners have the tool at their disposal. As such, positive academic performance follows naturally. In the process, learners become better positioned to perform well as they advance to their matric level and gradually acquire the linguistic and cognitive skills they will need beyond matric to handle their future job placement interviews (Albakri, 2017). This stands as sufficient evidence to confirm the pragmatic or utilitarian significance of using English as a LoLT, as envisaged by the CAPS (2011) curriculum.

Against this background, this study was aimed at exploring the teaching and learning patterns that emerge in Grade 10 classrooms when English is used as LoLT. This was achieved by assessing how the use of English as LoLT results in a crippling learning culture among Grade 10 learners in rural high schools. The findings derived from the study helped to provide learners with a missing first-hand voice in the current literature about their feelings, challenges, and the frustration they encounter in the process of learning English as an additional language. It helped to close the gap in the literature where the focus is mainly on educators, disregarding that learners have different experiences about the use of English as LoLT.

2. Background

Since this paper aims to explore the patterns that develop a crippling learning and teaching culture in Grade 10 EFAL, numerous studies focusing on this theme were consulted. A study by Riley (2007 p. 75), outlines that culture is a "sum of knowledge, beliefs, values and skills" that a sociocultural group, speech community or society applies, shares, and transmits to oncoming generations, to make sense of their way of life, in a given situation.

In corroboration, Aldawood and Almeshari's (2019) view of culture as a social practice denotes a way of life that defines a sociocultural group's habits and norms and endorses their perceptions and attitudes. They also noted that because of the culture's cognitive and affective nature, it plays an influential role in determining what it deems acceptable or unacceptable conduct. In the context of this study, the learning and teaching culture under exploration refers to the nature of classroom practice that teachers and learners create over time as a product of how they react to the use of English as a LoLT. Our discussion below focuses on the role played by linguistic, perceptual, affective, and contextual factors towards the emergence of the patterns that develop the crippling teaching and learning culture in EFAL classrooms.

2.1. Teachers' attitudes on the use of English vs indigenous languages

Studies conducted by Spokazi et al. (2021), Gumbi (2021), and Kretzer and Kaschula (2021) on language policy implementation in South African schools indicate that most teachers advocate for the use of English as a LoLT. They play a critical role in influencing learners and parents to choose English as a LoLT rather than using indigenous languages. The reason for the neglectful, biased attitude against indigenous languages is that they view English as a symbolic representation of power (Spokazi et al., 2021). That is, English LoLT is tied to their belief that English is a universal language they should develop in their learners to meet global needs in future. This explains why teachers feel justified in their adoption of English as the LoLT for their classes.

Hence, the code-switching is the cultural LoLT of many schools in the provinces highlighted above. Even teachers who are not proficient in English as a second language still struggle and code-switch into their home language in the process. In a study by Nqoma et al. (2017), they observed that some teachers were not relatively proficient in teaching in English as the LoLT, although they prefer it as the medium. Nqoma et al. (2017) further probed into this limited proficiency deficiency, but out of denial, the teachers defended themselves on the claim that they use code-switching for the benefit of their learners. It is therefore important to evaluate effective strategies that can be employed to ensure that teaching and learning take place effectively in EFAL classrooms. The question remains, why do they complicate things when they have a constitutional LiED policy and translingual pedagogies as available resorts?

2.2. The effect of limited linguistic skills

Several researchers who studied the use of English as a LoLT in and beyond South African schooling contexts, found that effective interactive learning is almost impossible where learners lack basic linguistic skills to understand or speak in the language (Ibrahim & Ibrahim, 2017; Humphries et al., 2020; Kretzer & Kaschula, 2021; Ipinge & Banda, 2020; Nqoma et al., 2017). These researchers unanimously agree that learners' limited or lack of linguistic skills mostly takes away learners' participatory voice and anticipated active learning. Among the critical examples of linguistic factors that limit learners' accuracy and fluency when called to participate in interactive activities in the classroom are limited knowledge of grammar, poor vocabulary, and pronunciation (Ork et al., 2024). Banda's (2020) view of the silence that often arises when learners struggle with language is that it is not only a reflection of their battle with accuracy and fluency, but also a signal of their struggle to grasp the content being taught.

This observation may not necessarily be attributed to learners' battle with understanding their teachers' instruction due to the latter's failure to modify

their input for easy access, but it could sometimes suggest teachers' lack of the level of proficiency they need to articulate the meaning of the concepts they are teaching (Mamabolo, 2021; Nqoma et al., 2017). This suggests that using an L2 to teach non-native learners does limit their cognitive development and academic access (Mataka & Taibu, 2020); and this is sadly often picked very late when learners are given assessment tasks or exams. A study by Aiello et al. (2025) that was conducted in Italy found results that are similar to those of most students who learn English as a second language. Their results highlight that although students show positive improvement when content-integrated language learning is applied, they still resort to memorisation as a strategy to improve proficiency in English. It is therefore essential that language planners evaluate the performance of learners who learn through EFAL or ESL and make recommendations.

2.3. The role of perceptions

A study by McDonald (2011, p. 8) defines perception as "an individual's or group's unique way of viewing a phenomenon." This starts with receiving a stimulus, then follows feeling, or experiencing it, through one's five senses, then processing it by comparing it with similar previous experiences before naming it and taking action. Individuals, groups or entities co-construct their own or a group's perception that results in them holding together to affirm their shared culture based on their beliefs or practices in a sociocultural environment.

Against this backdrop, a perception functions as a reflective tool that teachers and learners use to weigh their classroom practice and decide on how to receive or reject it and move forward. For example, the decisions to adopt or reject EMI in the educational contexts of Arabia and Pakistan were driven by students' perceptions of the policy in place. Firstly, in Alazemi's (2020) study, Arabic students in Kuwaiti classrooms opposed endorsing EMI because they viewed it as a tool used to disempower them by replacing their language. Secondly, in Masri's (2020) study, Arabic university youth in AEU also rejected EMI on the grounds that it was threatening to erode their heritage. They, therefore, fought against the use of English to protect their faith identity. Thirdly, in Asif et al.'s (2018) case in Pakistan, students reproached their own peers for embracing the use of English in a way that contradicts their community or language group's beliefs. They argued that their peers violated their community solidarity by inclining towards EMI at the expense of showing their loyalty to their HL. This was interpreted as an act of betraying their linguistic birthright in favour of a foreign language community. What stands out in the above illustration is that perceptions play a critical role in shaping attitudes, practices, or a peculiar culture in a sociocultural context.

In the context of our paper, we believe that since learners are thinking beings, the social injustice that they often encounter in their lessons when teachers compel them to speak unprepared, using English as a LoLT, does not go by without a thought, and such thoughts determine what they do next, whether positive or not. Hence, the crippling learning-teaching culture that is prevalent in their classrooms remains a product of their perception, and needs them to make choices and take decisions about what, when and how they will manage it (Lamatokan, 2018). Hence, it is important to conduct a study of this nature to find out the feeling of both learners and teachers.

2.4. Affective factors in additional language learning

According to Krashen (1982), interactive language learning is a process riddled with various emotions that aid or inhibit learners' effective learning during the lesson. On one end of the continuum, the process shows learners the glory and rewards of having a sound level of proficiency, while on the other end, it exposes them to emotional explosions and frustration induced by peer shaming and heartlessness. For this reason, the role of a teacher is to use their knowledge of positive emotions or affective factors, such as motivation, empathy and a positive attitude (Wang & Wu, 2020), to create and maintain an enabling atmosphere to keep learners' willingness to participate in the interactive activities. They further note that a learner's reaction in class is mostly a product of a chain of progression of effects from one effect to the other, which produces the final visible action. It begins with a thought (cognition), then an emotion (affection), and concludes with a reaction (intention).

Evidence drawn from researchers that explored the effect of affective factors in L2 learning (Humphries et al., 2020; Ork et al. 2024; Wang & Wu, 2020) identified several factors that play a critical role in the learning process, and these include fear, anxiety, inhibition, low self-esteem, motivation, doubt, and being shy. Ork et al. (2024) argue that these factors make learners opt to be silent to avoid committing language errors and the anticipation of the possibility of being mocked thereafter. They mostly heighten the affective filter and evoke the tension that impedes/blocks input intake or effective production of output during interaction.

2.5. The role of context

The learning context plays a critical role, across the curriculum, in determining learners' level of academic access and success (Desai, 2016; Madiba & Mabiletja, 2008; Probyn, 2005). This refers to the learners' individual socioeconomic background, as well as the nature of the elementary and secondary education they have received. This is in consideration of the

material and infrastructural resources a school has, and what it stands to offer in terms of scaffolding or inhibiting learners from effective learning. In the context of this study, the rural learning context contributed, in one way or another, to the basis upon which the crippling learning culture that learners face was developed.

As Probyn (2005) noted, the kind of learning environment learners find themselves in not only lays out the linguistic repertoire the school has, but also predicts the linguistic challenges they stand to face, in terms of the LoLT to be applied therein. In the context of EFAL learning and the challenges learners experience in a given context, no one can explain their situation without a clear reference to the contextual understanding of the realities learners face therein (Madiba & Mabiletja, 2008). Probyn (*ibid*) outlines the nature of learning contexts in which schooling in the South African context operates.

The influential role of learning context, such as private, township, urban and rural-based schools, in determining learners' educational access and success is illustrated in several studies (Madiba & Mabiletja, 2008; Desai, 2016; Ojo & Mathabathe, 2021) reviewed for this study. Desai's (2016) study of the medium of instruction in the Western Cape schools revealed that the effect of context can either enable or disable effective learning when English is used as a LoLT by non-native English-speaking learners. Her study revealed that learners' reactions to instruction differ from one context to another due to various reasons and circumstances. Some researchers believe that the government's unequal distribution of funds and resources is a plausible justification for schools' contextual differences (Madiba & Mabiletja, 2008; Ojo & Mathabathe, 2021). As a result, this creates a wide access and success gap between schools in different contexts. A good example illustrating this is reported in Ojo's (2021) study, which sought to establish the effectiveness of the CAPS curriculum when applied in private and public schools. The results of Ojo's (2021) study showed that there is a very wide gap in the way private and public-school learners access and use their teachers' input for effective learning in their classrooms, and beyond. Because of their advanced language proficiency, better material, economic, and human resources, private school learners have an advantage over those in public schools. Their learning through the CAPS is smooth, and it sets them up for better academic performance. This confirms Lafon's (2009, p. 8) assertion that "the better resourced a school is, the higher the chances of it producing better results." Conversely, most academically gifted learners in public schools get their destinies cut off far too early in their lives because of being socioeconomically ill-resourced.

Overcrowded classes also play a limiting and distractive role in learners' access to education. According to the SASA Act 1996: 3.24, a standard class size should

not exceed 40 learners. Overcrowding makes the classroom chaotic and hard to monitor or to give quality attention to individual learners (Du Plessis & Letshwene, 2020; Kretzer & Kaschula, 2020). Overcrowding is more prevalent in rural areas compared to urban areas, and this also contributes to the issue of unequal opportunities. To achieve the dream of providing quality education to all learners, the government must expedite the process of building classes and ensure that the teacher-learner ratio is balanced.

3. Theoretical framework

We adopted an eclectic theoretical framework comprising Vygotsky's (1978) Sociocultural Theory (SCT) and Krashen's (1981) Second Language Acquisition (SLA) theory, of which we focused on two of the latter's five hypotheses—the Input and Affective-filter hypotheses. Based on SCT's main claim, that learners' language and cognitive skills develop through social interaction in a sociocultural environment (Lightbown & Spada, 2013), we turned this claim into a lens to illuminate the emerging social patterns that develop a learning culture that cripples effective learning when English is used as a LoLT. On the other hand, our adoption of Krashen's theoretical hypotheses was meant to offer us an angle through which we would explore the nature and effect of the input teachers give out in their lesson delivery, and to identify and articulate the affective factors that evoke learners' silence, when English is used as a LoLT. This was done to augment SCT's silence on the articulation of the role affective factors play, and the impact they have on learners' willingness to speak during interactive lessons.

Through the blending of the two theories, it helped to evaluate the extent to which learners' cultural patterns were infused into the learning activities designed. Furthermore, it examined the level of comprehensibility of the input given compared to the cognitive level of the grade that was observed. Finally, it assessed the role teachers and advanced learners played to scaffold struggling learners/peers during the during EFAL classes. This is in line with the sociocultural SCT's argument that human cognition is gradually developed by an individual's engagement in the social and cultural activities with knowledgeable people.

4. Method

4.1. Study design

Given the social nature of this phenomenon, we employed a qualitative research approach to elicit participants' explications of their lived experiences. The approach provided us with various perspectives to access participants' firsthand accounts of their feelings, subjective interpretations, and frustration, without relying on non-numerical data (Walliman, 2016). The multiple nature

of the case study we used allowed us to note the similarities and differences that emerged as we visited the schools in their separate environments (Gustafson, 2017). Additionally, it helped us to draw a sound conclusion based on the data collected from different schools that using data from one school. This played a critical role in increasing the credibility of the findings ultimately (Leedy et al., 2019).

4.2. Population and sampling

The study population comprised 515 ($N = 550$) Grade 10 learners from three schools in the Hlanganani Central circuit office. A total of 15 learner participants, within the age range of 15-19, were purposively selected from the population, having been deemed eligible due to their sharing characteristic qualities relevant to answering the problem being studied (Cresswell & Cresswell, 2018). These were selected because they were part of the group of learners who mostly preferred to remain silent in class and would rather use their HL rather than English only when compelled to speak in class. These learners mostly performed below average in their English assessment tasks, especially in oral assessments. Additionally, 4 EFAL teachers responsible for teaching these learners were selected as participants.

4.3. Data collection instruments and procedure

The data collection instruments we utilised comprised observation, focus group interview, and semi-structured interview. These were only used after all ethical protocols were fulfilled, which entailed writing letters to all gatekeepers to request access to the research site, and to secure teachers' and parents' signed informed consent/and minor learners' assents forms.

4.3.1. Classroom observations

Classroom observation was utilised to ascertain the learning and teaching patterns that emerge when English is used as a LoLT in the three selected schools. This allowed us to watch the participants closely and note the kind of social patterns that arose to see how they related to the phenomenon being explored (Christensen et al., 2020; Johnson & Christensen, 2020). We observed six classes, broken down to two sessions per school, involving four teachers. The first two schools used one teacher to teach two classes, while the third one had two teachers who had their separate classes each. In this case, only one class was observed per teacher. Each observation visit lasted for an hour. We opted to take the largest and lowest number of learners per school, with a view to seeing how the class size variation would affect the learning process, as attested by Desai (2016). We assumed a non-participant observation role to allow proceedings to unfold naturally without influencing participants' natural

conduct. This arrangement gave us ample time to sit back and familiarise ourselves with the participants (Buckingham, 2016; Christensen et al., 2020), while observing all the proceedings without interruptions, to eliminate any potential development of observer's paradox (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). We used a semi-structured observation schedule we prepared beforehand to help us stay focused and consistent across the various schools visited, while we kept our eyes open to unplanned emerging data.

4.3.2. Focus group interviews

We used focus group interviews (FGI) to solicit learners' views, feelings, and difficulties they encounter when they use English as LoLT. We had our FGI sessions with Grade 10 learners in a specially arranged quiet classroom organised by their teachers for us. Each session involved 5 learners, based on each of the three selected schools. We had one FGI session per school. The interviews were strategically organised to occur during break, to avoid interrupting their lessons. Each session lasted between 30-45 minutes. Just like in the observation, the focus of our open-ended questions was placed on exploring the nature of classroom practice; the LoLT generally used; teaching-learning patterns triggered using the LoLT; learners' reactions to the use of English, and learning atmosphere triggered.

For our communication with learners during the FGI, we tactically used the learners' predominant home language, Xitsonga, in the first half of our discussion. We did this to create a conducive atmosphere to help them relax and talk to us freely, so they could speak directly from their hearts. We then shifted from using Xitsonga to English midway through the interview, but still kept communication open for code-mixing. This was aimed at assessing learners' level of language proficiency in English, their participation rate, emotional reaction, and the mediation techniques they employ to manage the conversation in English. Through the parents' and learners' permission, we audio-recorded all the interview sessions we conducted, while also taking field notes as backup.

4.3.3. Semi-structured interviews

A semi-structured interview was used to gather teachers' views on the experiences and challenges they encounter with the use of English as LoLT. This involved the 4 teachers, selected purposively from the three high schools, and each session lasted between 30-45 minutes. Our interviews were conducted face-to-face with each teacher, in the quiet venues each organised for the meeting, during their breaks or free periods. Using face-to-face interviews allowed us to observe much more than what a questionnaire would offer. For example, where participants would sometimes give verbal claims

that their own non-verbal gestures would not support, face-to-face was able to reveal the unsaid truth through facial expression, or other non-verbal gestures. As Dornyei (2007) would remark, interviews provide more room for probing for more information beyond what is planned on paper, during the exchange of ideas. All interview sessions were recorded using an audiotape, with permission obtained from the teachers, and backed up with hand-written notes, as advised by Creswell and Creswell (2018).

4.4. Data analysis

We employed inductive thematic content analysis (TCA) to analyse the three sets of data we collected through classroom observation, learners' focus group interviews, and teachers' semi-structured interviews. Opting for the inductive route aimed to gather raw data that would generate its own new themes, rather than relying on preconceptions drawn from previous studies (Kampira, 2021). Our analysis approach was guided by our adherence to the five sequential steps of thematic data analysis, which several authors recommend (Buckingham, 2016; Creswell & Guetterman, 2019; Fouche et al., 2021).

We started by listening repeatedly to the recorded audio tapes of learners' focus group interviews gathered from the three schools, to familiarise ourselves with the data. We then transcribed the audios to facilitate the execution of the next step, which is coding the data. Recurrent patterns began to emerge in the coding process, leading to various clusters of subthemes as we further analyse the data. These led to the creation of the final themes. Additionally, we analysed our written observation notes to see how they relate to the observation schedules we used to gather them. In this way, we were able to match what we gathered with what we had lined up in our observation schedule. Of significance was that the categories that emerged from this analysis of observation data were in alignment with the themes identified in the analysis of the focus group interview findings, about the patterns that emerge when English is used as a LoLT in Grade 10 EFAL classrooms.

5. Findings and discussion

This study was aimed at exploring the learning and teaching patterns that develop a crippling learning culture when English FAL is used as a LoLT in Grade 10 EFAL classrooms in rural schools. Based on the empirical data derived from observation, learners' focus group interviews, and teachers' semi-structured interviews, the following findings were established: language attitude, classroom practice, induced silence, learners' chaotic reactions, teachers' harmful scaffolding, and learners' withdrawal from oral assessment activities and class attendance. These findings are important in helping

language planners and educators to reassess the use of English in rural schools so that they can develop remedial strategies.

5.1. Language attitude and classroom practice

All data sources revealed that most teachers have a negative attitude towards their learners' need to use their L1 or a bilingual L2 in English lessons. This is confirmed by teachers' flat disapproval below:

I don't feel good about it. So, I don't allow that. (Excerpt 1: Edu 1 SCH A)

I don't like it because it is going to be problematic for them going forward. From where I come from, hm, we discourage it. You will find that learners seem to understand a certain topic when you code-switch, but when exam questions come, they struggle, hm. (Excerpt 2: Edu 2 SCH B)

It is clear in the way the two teachers' disapproving attitude resists the adoption of a bilingual pedagogy in their classrooms, and this accounts for the silence that ensues on the part of learners who do not have a sound command of the English LoLT to engage in participatory learning in their classrooms. While the curriculum's idea is to create a supportive learning atmosphere to encourage a participatory approach for all learners, teachers' insistence on using a monolingual LoLT creates a mismatch within the policy itself. One of the principles driving the policy is social transformation. The policy cannot achieve its transformation agenda while practising linguistic marginalisation in the classroom context

The study further revealed that, while the teachers' wishes stand opposed to those of the learners, the language practice applied in class does not benefit learners. This can be attributed to the fact that teachers have a negative attitude towards bilingual policy, and they ensure that English is used as the LoLT even when they realise that learners do not cope. Another challenge observed is that most teachers are not fluent in English, yet they insist that teaching must be conducted in English. On the other hand, learners acknowledge that English must be used as LoLT, but teachers must also clarify any concepts that learners fail to understand in class. They also noted that their teachers always initiate their lessons in English, but do not proceed further before the learners request them to switch to Xitsonga for a more meaningful explanation. The learners' responses below depict the language practice in EFAL classrooms.

We use English as the medium of instruction in our English classes and other subjects. But the Venda teachers use English only. They don't

switch to other languages, maybe because they can't speak Xitsonga. (Excerpt 3: Jack SCH A)

We use English; but teachers explain the meaning of what we are learning in Xitsonga. We ask them in Xitsonga, to explain what we don't understand. (Excerpt 4: Sam SCH C)

In most cases I use English, but have to explain sometimes in Xitsonga, because our learners are not fluent in English. They can't understand some of the English words. So, I need to give clarity in Xitsonga. Yes, we are supposed to use English; but if we can use English only, the pass rate will be very low. (Excerpt 5: Edu 3 SCH B)

Based on the responses above, it is clear that though the EFAL lessons always start in English through teachers' initiative, the use of the English LoLT is not sustained to the extent that it entirely excludes learners' indigenous language, as prescribed in the CAPS policy document and the school language policy. This is because the level of language proficiency learners possess is too limited to last the whole period. As a result, learners always ask their teachers to code-switch or translate what they are saying to Xitsonga as a strategy to help them understand the content presented. It is only then that learning begins to flow effectively in Xitsonga, and not Tshivenda, because the majority of learners in the schools speak Xitsonga as their first language. Xitsonga then becomes a mediation tool, essentially applied when learners get stuck linguistically midway through their output. In Section 5.2 below, the responses generated from the teacher participants confirm the description of the language practice highlighted in this section.

5.2. Harmful scaffolding and learners' chaotic reaction

The evidence gathered through teachers' interviews indicates that teachers do scaffold their learners towards the envisaged Zone of Proximal Development. However, by their own admission, the diverse approaches they apply either fall short or go beyond acceptable limits according to their learners. This study reveals that they scaffold by forcing their learners to participate in the interactive lessons against their will. This is done in the belief that if learners are not encouraged, they may not voluntarily take the initiative and risk their chances. In their own words, they show here how they do it. In response to the question of how they personally scaffold their learners, the following comments came up:

Most of the time I just call the learner and try to understand what the main reason is. Most of them the reason they gave me is that they are scared that some learners might at laugh at them. They ask what if they

could do it privately or in the staff room, but I tell them no, it has to be done in the classroom so that they would get to practice. (Excerpt 6: Edu 1 SCH A)

You know, normally, you make them feel that they are part of the team. You try to encourage them, not judge them. That is one thing; and you don't embarrass them. You talk to them individually sometimes. Sometimes you opt to just pick any learner from the silent ones and tell them to give you the answer. You will be surprised how they correctly answer the questions. (Excerpt 7: Edu 2 SCH B)

While the comments above show that teachers go an extra mile to scaffold their learners, the same teachers almost immediately nullify their effort by changing their strategies and pounce on their learners who feel they are not ready to speak. This is problematic and unlawful in the sense that the act of forcing learners to talk against their will by pushing them into participating amounts to abusive behaviour. As a result, those who were picked to speak against their will would speak ungrammatically and meaninglessly, and embarrass themselves, while a handful of others failed to utter a single word.

This has a negative impact on learners with low proficiency in the English language. Some of them feel ashamed when they fail to express themselves, as their classmates capitalise on the situation and laugh at them rather than show them any empathy and encouragement. To make matters worse, a lot of other irresponsible learners would take advantage of the overcrowded nature of the class, with over 70 learners, and veer off the lesson to talk about other things unrelated to the lesson in progress, since the teacher is not able to move around due to the small size of the classroom.

Hm, yo-yo, class size, especially Maths and Science group, they are many. That one is overcrowded, it's two classes in one. When they are many, I can't move around to take some of their books to mark. If someone is making noise here, when you reprimand them here, some would be making noise on the other side. You can't even move around. It does affect performance because if a teacher wants to go help someone at the back, s/he can't. He or she can only help the ones close to him. (Excerpt 8: Edu 4 SCH B)

One of the greatest challenges in South African schools is overcrowding. Even teachers who are energetic and fluent in English are hindered from presenting their lessons effectively due to overcrowding. They fail to move around in the class to guide learners and provide individual attention. This crippling learning atmosphere mostly ends with the victimised opting to bunk classes, those who remain opt to be silent, while the worst affected would express their

frustration by fighting their teachers physically or drop out of school to guarantee their own emotional protection.

Based on the comment above, the classroom size is one of the contextual challenges teachers contend with; it limits the space for organising pair or group work to effect collaborative learning structures, and teachers' movement for lesson facilitation. Some learners engage in unlawful behaviour, as they know that their teachers cannot easily move around the class and punish them for their actions. As a result, it allows learners to engage in chaotic conduct as a gesture of rejection of being coerced into speaking against their will. The challenge is that the government keeps promising to establish classes so that all learners can have quality education in decent classrooms.

5.3. Learners' induced silence

The results obtained from both classroom observation and teachers' and learners' interview concur that limited language proficiency not only makes learners flout grammatical accuracy, but also makes them distort intended meaning in the process. This usually results in limited knowledge being transferred in class or creating a situation where the meaning of the information presented in class being flawed. The remarks given by participants below are illustrative:

Speak English? In class? Eish, others in class, they are laughing at me; so I am not feeling well. (Excerpt 9: Magezi C)

Yoh, some of them ... some of them really can't speak English. They don't want to do orals, because they are afraid of speaking in public; but with Xitsonga orals they do, with English is a problem. They don't want that. They would say ma'am just give zero. It's fine'. That's what they do. (Excerpt 10: Edu 4 SCH C)

Based on learners' responses above, it is clear that the use of the English LoLT severely limits the expression of their thoughts when classroom activities are conducted orally. This comes in different forms, as reflected in Magezi's statement above, such as producing very short, fragmented and ungrammatical sentences. Such errors, where meaning is flouted midway through the sentence in public, mostly subject them to peer mockery, which discourages them from engaging in classroom participation in the future.

Additionally, the study also found that learners' silence is induced by various inhibiting affective factors, both before and while they are producing their output. These include anxiety, fear, low self-esteem or being shy. Silence is intensified by the fact that speaking in a public platform does not give them enough time to ponder on grammatical accuracy and fluency while people are

eagerly waiting for their output. This, therefore, piles more pressure on their shaken confidence, doubt and frustration. Besides, the fact that they rarely find themselves anywhere else beyond their schoolyards or communities that are input-charged to compel them to practise using English or to test their hypothesis (Swain, 2019) also makes them doubt their level of fluency, since they hardly ever hear themselves speak. This is depicted in Jack's statement below:

“Marimi ma hina a ma tolovelanga ku vulavula Xinghezi.” [our tongues are not used to speak in English]. (Jack's statement)

Afraid. But in my heart, I will like hm I'm gonna rock it, but yo, when I go to the front neh, then they start laughing before I could say anything, the fear gets worse. So, I give up. (Excerpt 11: Basani SCH A)

It breeds silent classes or groups of learners who may either create chaos in class or remain uninterested while in class, which is detrimental to effective learning. In the context of this study, some learners bunk classes or assessment activities to avoid embarrassment or feeling inadequate in front of their peers. This has a negative impact because it results in school dropout for some learners who fail to improve their proficiency in English.

This reality has various limiting effects; it not only makes it almost impossible for learners to participate in the oral activities teachers give them but also creates intrapersonal dialogue within the affected learners. Silence in class, as revealed through data sources, also signifies anxiety or fear of committing errors before learners who are always ready to shame their peers. The worst part of learners' silence in class is that teachers may not be able to measure their learners' language development in terms of communication and critical thinking growth. Therefore, teachers work in darkness, and only get their feedback when learners write their exams, which is always too late.

6. Conclusion

The aim of this study was to explore the teaching and learning patterns that emerge in Grade 10 classrooms when English is used as LoLT, with a view to ascertaining how they develop a crippling learning culture in rural high schools. All the data sources used in this study revealed a unanimous observation that the exclusive use of English as a LoLT by learners who hardly understand the language makes it hard for them to comprehend the content being taught. This study identified several learning and teaching patterns that gradually combine to create a crippling learning culture, making effective learning in English classrooms almost impossible in most rural areas. These include language attitude, induced silence, and teachers' harmful scaffolding

approach, which triggers learners' chaotic reactions, with resultant withdrawal from oral assessment activities, class attendance and ultimate dropping out of school.

Our conclusion thus is that there is a need for teachers to show an empathetic attitude towards their learners who battle using English as LoLT. This will help them work out a way in which they can protect rather than expose themselves to shame and mockery by their peers when they find out that their learners have low proficiency in English. Additionally, translingual pedagogy is a critical option they should consider embracing because it is beneficial in reducing learners' affective filters (Yafele & Motlhaka, 2021) and demands very little in terms of polished proficiency in English. It also boosts learners' confidence and encourages them to share ideas using both English and their first language without fear.

7. Recommendations

Since this study confirmed that the underlying trigger of learners' silence and emotionally traumatising learning atmosphere in EFAL classrooms is the use of the English LoLT, we recommend that teachers adopt translingual pedagogy as it resonates with learners' language practice in their communities. This will help lower their learners' affective filter (Krashen, 1981) and immediately restore learners' confidence and willingness to participate actively in the language of their choice or ability.

Individual language teacher agency is critically essential as a tool to help teachers renounce long-standing stereotypes. Teachers who view themselves as social justice agents should pluck up their courage to do this, and may as well be trusted to be the ones who will also encourage their learners to exercise individual autonomy (Tao & Gao, 2021), as they pursue their improvement of their English proficiency-linked dreams. This move will benefit the learners who struggle to cope when English is used as the LoLT in class.

Authors' Statement

Chauke is responsible for writing sections 1, 2, 2.1, 2.2 and 2.5, 4, 4.1, 4.2, 5 & 5.1, Maluleke is responsible for writing sections 2.3, 2.4, 4.3 & 5.2, Klu is responsible for writing the Abstract and sections 5.1, 6 & 7, and Sikitime is responsible for sections 3, 4.4 & 5.3.

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